

INTEGRATIVE ANALYTICS FOR ADVANCING DECISION SUPPORT IN RAIL-BASED FREIGHT TRANSPORT

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ABSTRACT

Although logistics are increasingly digitalized, challenges remain in monitoring and assessing rail service performance across end-to-end freight transport journeys, particularly due to limited traceability and the frequent neglect of performance indicators. Recent advancements in Intelligent Rail Transportation Systems (IRTS) leverage big data analytics to enhance railway operations and decision-making. However, there is still a lack of decision support systems to continuously monitor the efficiency, sustainability and resilience of rail end-to-end corridors, limiting the acquisition of an overarching view of service performance in an integrated manner. To address this ongoing gap, key challenges must be observed: (i) the integration of diverse data sources, encompassing both transport views at ports and corridors, for holistic analysis, (ii) the definition of key indicators and metrics (e.g. capacity shortages, delays, suboptimal loads) that capture service performance variability across time and space, and (iii) actionable approaches to ensure robust machine learning and statistical analysis to enhance observability of spatiotemporal pattern dynamics in the scope of service performance of the different corridors.

Considering the above challenges, this research focus on the development of an advanced Analytical Decision Support System (ADS2) for the comprehensive identification and assessment of key performance indicators in rail freight systems such as capacity shortages, travel time, delays, suboptimal load factors. The system is designed to provide actionable insights for each journey by offering: (i) a tailored, multi-dimensional metric system that evaluates service quality (e.g., average delay times at entry and exit points, capacity, travel time, empty trips, and suboptimal transfer time); (ii) context-sensitive analytics that capture temporal trends and seasonal patterns across various terminal locations; (iii) capabilities to assess service

suitability for different types of goods (e.g., hazardous cargo, perishable goods); and (iv) a ranking system that aggregates end-to-end journeys according to their mobility dynamics for comparing service quality standards. The case study in this research focuses on the evaluation of services in the national freight system that connects the multimodal Port of Sines with key cargo destinations, which includes the Sines-Madrid multimodal corridor. The proposed tool aims to support an effective transport planning – operational, tactical and strategic – to foster the connection between rail services and the logistics operations at the Port of Sines, addressing the entire supply chain.

Keywords: Decision Support System; Key Performance Indicators; Integrative Analytics; Rail Freight; Intelligent Supply Chains; Origin-Destination.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing focus on the sustainability and resilience of freight logistics has positioned railway corridors as a critical component of multimodal networks. Significant efforts have been made by policymakers to reduce the considerable disparity between the freight market, targeting a shift of cargo from road to rail freight [11, 24]. At the same time, the resilience of railway corridors is continuously challenged by novel regulations, fluctuating freight demand, freight and energy costs, and other operational and external pressures [28]. Considering these scenarios, there is an increasing need for adaptive strategies and investment in data-driven technologies to enable the continuous spatiotemporal monitoring and assessment of rail corridors [26]. With the digitalization of transport systems, including the sensorization and geolocalization of assets [3], key performance indicators (KPIs) can be used to continuously monitor operations across corridors and over time, thereby providing actionable business intelligence to the sector [17].

Conventional digital monitoring of rail freight corridors has primarily focused on depicting and analysing single-dimensional indicators, including delays and demand fluctuations per corridor [12, 7]. While useful, this approach fails to capture the multidimensional and spatio-temporal footprint of corridors [22], including actionable patterns with or without deviant behaviour. Particularly, patterns that show the interplay between efficiency, resilience, connectivity, and environmental sustainability. Moreover, existing tools seldom address the spatiotemporal evolution of corridor performance or provide flexible decision-support capabilities tailored to the specific needs of decision-makers [20]. Considering the existing gaps, several key challenges need to be addressed, including: (i) the integration of diverse data sources, encompassing transport operations at both ports and corridors, to enable a holistic analysis; (ii) the definition of key performance indicators and metrics (e.g., capacity shortages, seamless multimodality integration, suboptimal loads, energy consumption from fossil fuels, percentage of renewable energy used in the supply chain, among others) that capture service dynamics across time and per corridor; (iii) the application of robust machine learning and statistical analyses to enhance the observability of spatiotemporal pattern dynamics; and (iv) the development of decision-support systems with capabilities that allow decision-makers to explore different scenarios with flexibility.

To address these challenges, this study proposes a analytical decision-support system (ADS2) that integrates KPIs across multiple critical dimensions, as well as solid analytical facilities for establishing actionable signals and summaries (i.e. clustering-

based analytics). Grounded in dynamic and interactive KPI design principles, the tool's development is centred on the integration of KPIs. Moreover, the ADS2 enables a multidimensional and spatiotemporal assessment of rail freight corridors, offering actionable insights into terminals, corridors, and port logistics (viewed as rail terminals). By integrating flexible KPIs, their normalization and weighting procedures, the framework allows for composite performance measurement aligned with balanced strategic priorities, such as maximizing capacity utilization, reducing delays, or lowering emissions. Through this research contribution, the study advances along methodological and practical perspectives: it enriches the understanding of spatiotemporal corridor footprints and provides a decision-support tool capable of guiding infrastructure planning and policy evaluation.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews the existing literature and identifies principles for OD corridor monitoring; Section 3 outlines the methodological framework, detailing: (i) the functional KPIs employed in the case study, (ii) the data processing pipeline used to obtain the required temporal abstractions, (iii) the analytical model for knowledge generation (clustering), (iv) the data consolidation mechanisms that ensure interoperability as inputs for the decision support system, (v) the metric design for the synthetic generation of KPIs, and (vi) the visual aids that enable benchmarking and comparability across corridors, timeframes, and policy scenarios. Section 4 describes the dataset used. Section 5 presents the results, including validation of the descriptive model (clustering) and a demonstration of the decision support system in providing actionable insights. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the main conclusions.

2. RELATED WORK

The performance of OD corridors has long been a central concern in transport planning and freight transport operations. Recent studies underscore the growing importance of data-driven approaches and dashboard systems for monitoring key performance indicators [12, 7]. With the increasing sensorization of transportation networks, large-scale spatio-temporal datasets have become a crucial resource for providing timely and dynamic assessments of corridor performance [3, 27]. In this context, interactive dashboards and advanced analytics are emerging as essential tools to support practitioners and experts in decision-making processes. Building on the literature on analytics and visualization systems tailored to OD performance monitoring, a set of guiding principles can be identified: (i) robust data acquisition and consolidation, (ii) provision of functional and synthetic key performance indicators (KPIs), (iii) spatio-temporal abstraction (iv) data analytics. Considering these principles, the remainder of this section will examine each in turn and discuss how the existing literature has addressed each identified aspect.

Data acquisition and consolidation: Reliable corridor assessment requires integrating heterogeneous sources such as sensors, logistics records, and GPS traces. These can be structured in multi-dimensional schemes to support efficient analysis. For instance, [7] applies Snowflake and constellation schemas for Power BI reports on container flows in a major Portuguese port, while [18] employs a star schema enabling roll-up, drill-down, and slicing operations across space and time. Beyond traditional warehouses, consolidation may use relational databases, graph models, or document stores [25]. These systems can expose data in formats such as JSON or XML, which

makes them well-suited for integration through REST APIs [1], enabling interoperability across different services and organizations.

Functional and synthetic KPIs: Practitioners and experts devote significant effort to defining functional KPIs [17] that capture measurable aspects of corridor dynamics, thereby enabling targeted analysis aligned with mission objectives. These goals span multiple dimensions, including efficiency (e.g., travel time, reliability, throughput, or terminal dwell time), equity (affordability of services, market coverage, and access for small and medium-sized shippers), multimodality (intermodal share, interchange efficiency, and first/last-mile connectivity), sustainability/environmental impact (emissions per ton-kilometre, energy intensity), and safety (accident rates, disruption recovery time) [12, 29, 8]. While functional KPIs provide detailed insights, synthetic KPIs consolidate multiple measures into composite indices that enable higher-level interpretation and comparability across corridors, timeframes, and scenarios [12]. As highlighted by Jing et al. [12], extending dynamic visual analysis for synthetic indicators is a promising research direction, particularly when dealing with real-time and large-scale datasets. Methodological challenges in this area include the determination of appropriate weights across factors [16], the development of efficient computation methods, and the design of adaptive frameworks for rapidly changing conditions. From these considerations, a set of principles for dynamic and interactive KPI design can be derived: i) experts should be able to dynamically integrate any number of performance indicators (flexibility), ii) systems should provide functions to normalize heterogeneous indicators and assign weight factors transparently (normalization and weighting), iii) functional and synthetic indicators should be presented consistently benchmarking across corridors, timeframes, and policy scenarios (comparability), iv) both functional and synthetic KPIs should be continuously updated to reflect new data and changing conditions (dynamic synthesis).

Spatio-temporal abstraction: Typical approaches for visualizing patterns in spatio-temporal OD data include OD matrices [6], flow maps [9], OD maps [2], and OD time series [10]. In the design of such data structures, it is essential to establish an appropriate level of temporal and spatial aggregation or abstraction allowing the interpretability or the capacity to uncover meaningful patterns. In highly dense networks (e.g., with numerous stops/stations/hubs or rail routes), spatial abstraction becomes necessary. Three main strategies for spatial abstraction are commonly discussed in the literature: i) aggregation of OD zones into coarser zones using clustering algorithms such as DBSCAN or k-means [14]; ii) semantic aggregation based on administrative or planning units, such as Traffic Analysis Zones (TAZs) or other city-provided boundaries (e.g., GeoJSON definitions) [23, 6] and iii) aggregation of OD flows that can be either an offline aggregation, using trajectory clustering methods such as Traclus, which group similar movement patterns [9, 4]; or online, using edge bundling techniques [15], which dynamically merge spatially close flows to reduce overlaps in the visualization. Concerning temporal discretization, OD data can be represented at different time granularities. Namely fine-grained discretization (e.g., minutes or hours) or enables the detection of short-term variations such as rush hours or daily commuting peaks, but increases visual and cognitive complexity. A coarse-grained discretization (e.g., days, weeks, or months) highlights long-term patterns such as seasonal trends or persistent OD corridors. More advanced approaches employ adaptive time windows (defined by traffic periods) [23] or temporal clustering

to automatically identify meaningful intervals that balance detail and interpretability and sparsity [2].

Data analytics: Descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics are well established in the literature as principles for providing integrative knowledge and analysis of OD corridors [13, 7, 19, 30, 31]. Descriptive analytics encompass the identification of patterns in OD movements, such as temporal variations in demand, mode choice analysis across corridors, bottlenecks across OD corridors. In the scope of KPI analytics analysis, [21] proposes factor-cluster analysis to benchmark and compare Short Sea Shipping networks considering service, economic and environmental KPIs, highlight as results key cluster to explain OD corridor performance. Predictive analytics aim to forecast future conditions by leveraging historical and real-time data, supporting anticipatory decision-making in areas such as demand growth, service disruptions, or environmental impacts [30]. Prescriptive analytics extend this by recommending actionable strategies, for example optimizing capacity allocation, scheduling freight and passenger rail movements [13], or evaluating policy scenarios [31]. A further principle for knowledge generation about corridor performance concerns the explicit measurement of uncertainty in both data and models. Given the inherent stochastic nature of OD corridors and the limitations descriptive/predictive algorithms, analytics frameworks should quantify confidence intervals, error bounds, and sensitivity measures, providing transparency and the decisions can account for risks.

Considering these above principles grounded in the literature, the following section introduces a analytical decision support system for rail-based freight transport services.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology can be conceptualized as a pipeline that operates on precomputed data structures, integrating data processing, analytics, and visualization. The process begins with data preprocessing and consolidation, ensuring that inputs are consistent and interoperable. Subsequently, the pipeline generates an individual and integrative KPI schema, where functional indicators are selected, normalized, and weighted to produce composite performance measures. These representations support the corridors' representation layer, enabling clustering and dynamic visualization of corridor dynamics. Finally, the system provides ranking and cluster-based analysis, allowing systematic monitoring and comparative assessment of OD corridors over time.

3.1 Data Pre-processing and Clustering

OD records are pre-processed following a pipeline that includes aggregation, time-series construction, outlier detection, and disaggregation, as described below:

- *Spatial and temporal aggregation:* Records are grouped by OD corridor and aggregated (median values) over a parametrizable time interval ΔT , with a default duration of 24 hours.
- *Multivariate origin–destination time series:* For each aggregated statistic in s , the origin–destination records are chronologically ordered and aligned to form a multivariate time series for each OD corridor.

- *Handling outliers*: Outliers in the OD time series are detected using a moving-window approach. For each window of length w , records are evaluated against the rolling median and interquartile range (IQR). Observations that lie beyond predefined thresholds (e.g. $\pm 1.5 \times \text{IQR}$) are flagged as outliers and subsequently either removed or replaced with interpolated values. This approach is particularly suitable for KPI-based time series, as it accounts for short-term variability while preserving underlying trends.
- *Daily disaggregation*: The cleaned and consolidated OD time series, under a default daily granularity, are then inputted for subsequent machine learning analysis.

The preprocessing pipeline applied to the data yields a tabular dataset containing daily records for each OD corridor, encompassing multivariate statistics. Given the high number of instances per OD, an aggregated KPI-driven analysis of vulnerabilities is critical to acquire summarized views. To this end, several clustering methods are applied to the dataset, namely k-means, hierarchical clustering with various linkage criteria (single, complete, and average), and Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) to acquire summarized view of OD corridors performance. The similarity metric is configurable, with the Euclidean distance recommended due to the importance of KPI magnitudes, making it preferable to alternatives such as cosine similarity. The performance of the different methods is evaluated using the following internal metrics: sum of squared errors, silhouette score, Davies–Bouldin index and Calinski-Harabasz Index. The elbow method is also employed to identify the optimal number of clusters by analysing the inflection point at which adding more clusters no longer results in a significant reduction of the within-cluster variance (i.e., Sum of Squared Errors).

3.2 Interactive Dashboard

The proposed dashboard is organized into three main pages, each offering distinct functionalities. The first page allows the integration of summary data and KPIs, with support for customized and dynamic normalization and weighting settings. The second and third pages are dedicated to data visualization, offering interactive ways to explore and analyse the corridors. The overall structure is guided by a navigation bar with the following sections: (i) data upload and metrics/weights settings, (ii) corridor analysis, and (iii) OD corridor ranking. The structure and purpose of each section are described in detail in the following subsections.

3.2.1. Data Structures

In the current implementation, the dashboard relies on two precomputed data structures. The first structure provides hierarchical information on clusters and features, supporting the analysis and inspection of cluster profiles through aggregated statistical summaries of key performance indicators (KPIs) across operational, environmental, and performance metrics.

The second structure captures the temporal dynamics of OD corridors, representing both the sequence of cluster assignments over time and the evolution of multivariate statistics for each corridor. This organization enables the dashboard to analyse trends and patterns at the corridor level, including decompositions of time-series data into

trend, seasonal, and residual components. Detailed examples of the input formats are provided in Appendix A.1.

3.2.2. Metrics and Weighting Settings

The Metrics and Weighting Settings section enables transportation experts to configure how corridor performance is quantified and aggregated. Users can dynamically add one or more features, corresponding to the statistics provided in the first JSON structure, and adjust their normalization and weighting. These settings determine how individual metrics contribute to the composite performance score, including mechanisms to limit the influence of extreme values and prevent outliers from disproportionately affecting overall results (see Figure 1).

- *Min-Max*: Values between the lower and upper bounds (corresponding to the worst and best scenario inputs) are normalized to the [0, 1] range. Values below the lower bound are assigned a score of 0, and values above the upper bound are assigned a score of 1.
- *Piecewise*: Values are scaled to the [0, 1] range using a target (expected value, a) and a spread (maximum allowed deviation, b). Values near the target are assigned scores close to 1, while values deviating beyond the spread are assigned a score of 0.

Metric	Function	Worst Case	Best Case	Weight
Median Cargo Handling Time Min	Min-Max	578	170	0.167
Median CO2e Emissions Kg WW	Min-Max	1786	510	0.167
Median Capacity Utilization	Min-Max	68	93	0.167
Median Velocity Km H	Min-Max	21	26	0.167
Median Origin Delay Min	Min-Max	0	10	0.166
Median Destination Delay Min	Min-Max	0	10	0.166

Figure 1: Metrics and weights settings display

Based on the selected configuration (KPIs, normalization functions, bounds and weights), the composite performance score of corridor i at timestamp t is computed using:

$$S_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \cdot f(x_{ij}(t)), \quad 1$$

where $x_{ij}(t)$ is the value of feature j at time t , $f(\cdot)$ is the chosen normalization function, and w_j is the weight of feature j , with $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$. The resulting time series $\{S_i(t)\}$ represents the overall performance evolution of corridor i at timestamp t . Time series scores for each corridor are presented as visual aids, as described in Section 3.2.3.

3.2.3. OD Corridors Ranking

Considering the page that provides a comparative analysis of OD corridors, the user can dynamically select one or more OD corridors for performance evaluation, targeting efficiency or environmental issues, in a chosen a time window. Once the selection is made, two visualizations are generated: (i) a time series plot showing the evolution of composite performance scores over time (Figure 2), and (ii) a ranking chart of OD corridors based on their cumulative scores across the entire study period (Figure 3). A higher score reflects better performance with respect to the selected criteria. This functionality enables decision-makers to explore different scenarios and assess how corridors perform relative to each other under varying conditions, thereby supporting evidence-based planning and policy evaluation.

OD Pairs Performance

Time series scores for each selected OD pair, combined for comparison.

Figure 2: Illustrative example of Time series Ranking considering the selected OD Corridors.

Detailed Ranking

1	Sines → Entroncamento	Total Score: 9.7665
2	Sines → Bobadela	Total Score: 8.8094
3	Sines → Setúbal	Total Score: 7.2524

Figure 3: Overall ranking of OD corridors based on cumulative performance scores computed.

3.2.4. OD Analysis

The OD analysis page is designed to provide the user with a detailed examination of the selected OD corridor for moving freight. The interface prompts the user to choose an individual OD corridor and a temporal window for analysis, after which three visualizations are displayed. These visualizations provide actionable insight of OD dynamics, considering the KPI's treated according to pipeline described in section 3.1. The KPI's as exploratory analysis in the results are further described in section 4.1. The first visualization allows the user to select a specific metric to observe over the chosen period, along with its trend, seasonal, and residual components. Figure 4 illustrates this with the CO₂ [kg] WtW emissions of a corridor. The time series was derived from corridor configurations using an online emissions calculator [5] and subsequently decomposed with the TLS method to extract trend, seasonal, and residual structures.

Figure 4. Observed Time series of Co2 [kg] WtW median decomposed into Trend Seasonal and Residual components

The second visualization shows the temporal sequence of cluster labels, as illustrated in Figure 5. This sequence can be interpreted as a time series of categorical values, where each timestamp is assigned to a cluster representing a distinct network performance pattern. By examining the succession of these labels over time, users can identify recurring performance patterns, including abnormal days or periods, and analyse the stability or variability of corridor performance across different temporal scales.

Figure 5: Label sequence for the Entroncamento – Port of Sines corridor, highlighting its key footprints.

As third visualization, a series of cards is presented to enhance the explainability of the clusters appearing in the sequence (as shown in Figure 5). Each card summarizes the main statistical characteristics of a given cluster. The statistical information provided in each card consists of the median and interquartile range (IQR) for every feature, thereby offering a robust description of the central tendency and variability within each cluster. In addition, the composite score is displayed for the timestamps associated with the cluster (see below cluster numerical label), including the median and IQR. This approach enables decision-makers to assess both the reliability and stability of cluster assignments when interpreting temporal traffic patterns.

Features for Sequence Clusters

Key features for the unique clusters present in the selected sequence.

Figure 6. Summary of the main statistical characteristics for each cluster, presented via cluster cards, for the Entroncamento - Sines corridor.

4. CASE STUDY: THE MULTIMODAL CORRIDOR SINES-MADRID

The national rail connections to the Port of Sines in Portugal serve as the basis for empirical observation of service performance patterns and their interaction with the decision support system. JUL (Single Port Window) is a digital platform that connects entire national logistics chain, connecting land transportation, dry ports, and logistics platforms enabling share information in real time and align processes to ensure synchronized operations. As part of the research and innovation project ADMIRAL, the Port of Sines provided LNEC a sample dataset including OD national rail services to move containerized cargo that connect Port of Sines, from March 2022. In particular, the analysis focuses on freight rail logistics corridors connecting Sines with Valongo, Leixões, Entroncamento, Setúbal, and Bobadela terminals (inbound and outbound movements from Port of Sines). Additionally, fossil fuel consumption values (e.g., CO2e emissions) for each OD record were calculated using a benchmark emission calculator [5], which provides detailed information on emissions and energy use for different transport modes in accordance with ISO standards and the GLEC framework.

4.1. Statistical Measures of Rail Service

Considering the data provided by the Port of Sines and the emission calculator [5], relevant statistical measures for assessing rail corridors, including the following selected examples:

- *Demand*
 - Cargo Volume: Cargo measured in TEUs or tonnes transported by rail from point A to point B.
 - Hazardous Cargo Volume: Hazardous cargo measured in TEUs or tonnes transported by train from point A to point B.
 - Capacity: Percentage of the cargo load relative to the maximum cargo that can be transported from point A to point B.
- *Length*
 - Velocity: Average travel speed of the train between points A and B, computed as the ratio of total distance travelled to total transit time, including stops and operational delays. Higher values indicate faster service. Velocity is preferable for comparing travel times because it normalizes the duration by distance, allowing meaningful comparisons of service efficiency across corridors of varying lengths.
- *Reliability*
 - Origin Lag Time (Delay/Earliness): Difference between actual and scheduled times for rail at the departure time at point A. Negative values represent earliness.
 - Destination Lag Time (Delay/Earliness): Difference between actual and scheduled times for rail service arriving at point B. Negative values represent earliness.
- *Connectivity*
 - Cargo Handling Time: Time spent moving containers to the rail vehicle at point A.
- *Environmental Sustainability*
 - Greenhouse Gases: Greenhouse gas emissions generated by the vehicle from point A to point B are computed using an online emissions calculator [5], considering each OD movement setting. The extracted KPI indicators include CO₂e [kg] WTW, CO₂e Intensity [g CO₂e/tonne-km], and CO₂ [kg] WTW.

5. RESULTS

The findings are organized into two primary sections. The initial section validates the approach by assessing the effectiveness of clustering in identifying unique patterns of daily activity across OD corridors. The second section demonstrates the performance and dynamics of OD corridors through their integration into a decision support system.

5.1 Validation

Observing Figure 7, the K-means algorithm with eight clusters yields a Silhouette score of 0.5 and a Calinski–Harabasz index of 700. The elbow method also indicates that eight clusters correspond to the inflection point for the sum of squared errors. A higher number of clusters (e.g., 23) slightly improves separation according to the Calinski–Harabasz index. However, this solution does not necessarily enhance interpretability. Considering the Silhouette, Davies–Bouldin, and Calinski–Harabasz

indices together, eight clusters provide a balanced trade-off between cluster quality and interpretability.

Figure 7: Clustering evaluation metrics: (a) Silhouette Score, (b) SSE, (c) Davies-Bouldin Index, (d) Calinski-Harabasz Index.

5.2 Demonstration of the Decision Support System

This section presents an empirical analysis of the decision support system, focusing on the performance of each corridor in the national freight rail network. In addition, it highlights the most relevant patterns identified during the exploratory analysis.

5.2.1 Metrics and Weight Settings

The KPIs listed in Table 1 were selected for the initial demonstration scenario. Min-max normalization is applied to most KPIs, except for Origin Lag and Destination Lag Time (minutes), for which a piecewise function is used. This choice is motivated by the fact that the target value for these metrics is 0 (indicating no delay or earliness), with an acceptable spread of up to 10 minutes (the maximum expected deviation). The normalization bounds for the min-max function of each KPI were set according to the interquartile range (Q1–Q3) of the KPI distribution in the dataset.

Feature	Function	Best/Target	Worst/Spread	Weight
Cargo Handling Time	Min-Max	170	578	0.2
CO ₂ e [kg] WTW	Min-Max	510	1786	0.2
Capacity (%)	Min-Max	93	68	0.2
Origin Lag Time (min)	Target-based	0	10	0.2

Destination Lag Time (min)	Target-based	0	10	0.2
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Table 1. KPIs, functions, bounds and weights settings configured in ADS2.

Considering the settings in Table 1, the scenario aims to maximize capacity utilization and velocity, while minimizing CO2 emissions, cargo handling time, and delays or earliness at both the origin and destination points along the OD corridors.

5.2.2 Corridor analysis

Figures 8, 9, and 10 present three illustrative examples of the ten OD corridors analysed, showcasing their symbolic time series (cluster labels sequence) in March 2022.

Figure 8 illustrates the sequence for Setubal terminal to Port of Sines corridor. During the observation period, this corridor is consistently assigned to Cluster 1, indicating low variability in its operational behaviour. Table 2 summarizes the statistics for each KPI characterizing the clusters (these data appear at dashboard as shown in the Figure 5). Specifically, Cluster 1, exhibits no movements involving dangerous goods. The median total volume is 41 Twenty-foot Equivalent Units (TEUs), with a median cargo handling time of 161 minutes and a median capacity utilization of approximately 93%. Concerning delays/earliness, the median origin lag is 1.5 minutes earlier than anticipated, while the median destination lag indicates a delay of approximately 9 minutes. These values contribute to a median score of approximately 0.6, reflecting the cluster’s operational efficiency. These results indicate that the Setubal-Port of Sines corridor demonstrates a highly stable operational profile with moderate performance score, considering the chosen settings.

Figure 8. Label sequence from Corridor Setúbal Terminal to Port of Sines, illustrating a consistent footprint in Cluster 1.

Cluster 1 – Median [Q1; Q3]	
Score	0.64 [0.6; 0.74]
Dangerous Goods TEU	0 [0; 0]
Total TEU	41 [21; 44]
Cargo Handling Time	161 [52; 204]
CO₂e [kg] WTW	487 [417; 510]
Capacity (%)	93 [31; 100]
Velocity	25 [23; 28]
Origin Lag Time (Min)	-1.5 [-14; 4]
Destination Lag time (Min)	-9 [-30; 6]

Table 2. Summary statistics for Cluster 1, showing the median [Q1, Q3] values as presented in the dashboard for corridor Setúbal Terminal to Port of Sines.

Figure 9 illustrates the cluster sequence for the Entroncamento to Port of Sines corridor, a critical logistics route in Portugal. Entroncamento serves as a strategic terminal hub, transferring road cargo to rail and rail to rail. Throughout the observation

period in March 2022, the corridor’s behaviour alternates primarily between Clusters 3 and 5, with occasional assignments to Cluster 2.

The main characteristics of Clusters 3 and 5 are summarized in Table 3. Their key difference lies in median cargo volume (TEUs) and capacity utilization, with Cluster 3 showing lower throughput than Cluster 5. Cluster 2, by contrast, records much higher TEU volumes, longer handling times, and slower transit speeds. Cluster 2 also achieves the lowest performance score (median value of 0.3), indicating suboptimal efficiency compared to Clusters 3 and 5, which both reach median scores of about 0.4. The intermittent presence of cluster “2” demonstrates the corridor’s sensitivity to operational conditions periods, where capacity utilization exceeds typical levels, resulting in longer handling times, higher travel time, and increased delays at the destination.

Figure 9. Label sequence from Corridor Entroncamento to Port of Sines, highlighting Clusters 3, 5, and 2 as footprints of corridor dynamics.

	Cluster 3	Cluster 5	Cluster 2
	Median [Q1; Q3]	Median [Q1; Q3]	Median [Q1; Q3]
Score	0.42 [0.34; 0.48]	0.42 [0.37; 0.51]	0.33 [0.28; 0.38]
Dangerous Goods TEU	0 [0; 0]	0 [0; 2]	0 [0; 2]
Total TEU	46 [39; 55]	61 [55; 65]	70 [68; 71]
Cargo Handling Time	245 [180; 321]	237 [185; 367]	603 [540; 638]
CO₂e [kg] WTW	950 [837; 1004]	1336 [1218; 1410]	1112 [1088; 1152]
Capacity (%)	65 [55; 78]	84 [76; 89]	94 [91; 96]
Velocity	23 [21; 26]	26 [24; 28]	19 [19; 20]
Origin Lag Time (Min)	-7 [-16; 1]	-1 [-9; 5]	2 [-7; 6]
Destination Lag time (Min)	4 [-4; 25]	3 [-4; 13]	7 [3; 19]

Table 3. Summary statistics for Cluster 3, 5, and 2, showing the median [Q1, Q3] values as presented in the dashboard, for corridor Entroncamento to Port of Sines.

Figure 10 illustrates the cluster sequence for the Leixões to Port of Sines corridor, a key logistics route in Portugal, during March 2022. The corridor’s operational behaviour predominantly alternates between Clusters 4 and 7, with occasional assignments to Cluster 0, reflecting distinct patterns in cargo movement and operational performance.

Table 3 summarizes the multivariate statistics and performance metrics for the corridor. Unlike other corridors, this one handles a significant volume of hazardous cargo, with Clusters 4 and 7 reporting a median of 6 TEUs per day, while Cluster 0 shows no hazardous cargo movement. Total cargo volume, and thus CO₂ emissions, differs across the clusters, with median values of 64 TEUs, 55 TEUs, and 46 TEUs for Clusters 4, 7, and 0, respectively. Cargo handling times are notably longer in this corridor, with median values ranging from 611 to 620 minutes across the three clusters, compared to shorter times in other corridors. Transit speeds remain stable, with a median velocity of approximately 23 km/h across all clusters. Lead times relative

to schedules also vary. Clusters 4 and 7 have median origin lag times of 9 and 11 minutes, respectively, and median destination lag times of 19 and 11 minutes, respectively (all with IQR values below 0), indicating arrivals ahead of schedule. Moreover, Cluster 4 achieves the highest median performance score of 0.177, followed by Cluster 0 at 0.168, while Cluster 7 scores the lowest at 0.072, reflecting its lower operational efficiency handling Dangerous Cargo.

Figure 10. Label sequence from Corridor Leixões to Port of Sines, highlighting Clusters 4, 7, and 0 as footprints of corridor dynamics.

	Cluster 4	Cluster 7	Cluster 0
	Median [Q1; Q3]	Median [Q1; Q3]	Median [Q1; Q3]
Score	0.18 [0.12; 0.3]	0.07 [0.07; 0.13]	0.17 [0.08; 0.18]
Dangerous Goods TEU	6 [3; 9]	6 [0; 8]	0 [0; 0]
Total TEU	64 [62; 66]	61 [53; 56]	46 [44; 48]
Cargo Handling Time	620 [492; 642]	611 [386; 626]	615 [573; 651]
CO₂e [kg] WTW	2584 [2534; 2666]	2228 [2152; 2279]	1868 [1786; 1949]
Capacity (%)	85 [82; 90]	73 [71; 81]	79 [72; 84]
Velocity	23 [22; 23]	22 [21; 23]	23 [22; 23]
Origin Lag Time (Min)	-9 [-14; -3]	-11 [-19; -2]	13 [-3; 15]
Destination Lag time (Min)	-19 [-23; -5]	-11 [-28; 1]	1 [-24; 15]

Table 4. Summary statistics for Cluster 4, 7, and 0, showing the median [Q1, Q3] values as presented in the dashboard, for corridor Leixões to Port of Sines.

5.2.3 Corridors Ranking

Figures 11 and 12 illustrate examples of the dashboard visualization used to rank OD corridors, which can be dynamically selected by the user. Each figure represents a distinct evaluation scenario. For simplicity, Figure 11 displays the ranking based solely on CO₂ emissions, normalized using the Min–Max method with bounds defined between 510 and 1786 (corresponding to the first and third quartiles of the dataset). In this scenario, the Sines–Bobadela corridor (both inbound and outbound movements) achieves the highest score, followed by the Entroncamento–Sines and Leixões–Sines corridors. The order indicates that distance is the primary factor driving higher emissions levels across corridors.

Detailed Ranking

Sorted by Average Daily Score.

1	Sines → Bobadela	Score: 0.7933
2	Bobadela → Sines	Score: 0.6210
3	Sines → Entroncamento	Score: 0.5078
4	Entroncamento → Sines	Score: 0.4944
5	Sines → Leixões	Score: 0.1518
6	Leixões → Sines	Score: 0.0281

OD Pairs Performance Comparison

Time series scores for each selected OD pair, combined for comparison.

Figure 11. Corridor ranking based on CO₂ emissions, normalized with the Min–Max method using bounds from 510 to 1786.

Figure 12 presents the ranking based exclusively on the KPI of cargo handling time (i.e., the time required to transfer cargo to rail). Since the top three corridors all originate at the Port of Sines, the results suggest that this terminal demonstrates higher operational efficiency in handling rail transfers compared to other ports.

While these scenarios illustrate analyses based on a single KPI, the system also enables users to combine multiple KPIs to obtain a more comprehensive evaluation of corridor performance. Furthermore, ranking scores alone may not fully capture why one corridor performs better or worse than another. For this reason, the dashboard integrates clustering-based visualizations, providing a complementary perspective that explains the dynamics and underlying patterns of corridor operations.

Detailed Ranking

Sorted by Average Daily Score.

1	Sines → Entroncamento	Score: 0.8169
2	Sines → Bobadela	Score: 0.7125
3	Sines → Leixões	Score: 0.5075
4	Entroncamento → Sines	Score: 0.4263
5	Bobadela → Sines	Score: 0.0436
6	Leixões → Sines	Score: 0.0000

OD Pairs Performance Comparison

Time series scores for each selected OD pair, combined for comparison.

Figure 12. Corridor ranking based on cargo handling time, normalized with the Min–Max method using bounds from 170 to 512.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study undertakes the development of an Analytical Decision Support System (ADS2), focused on the integration of multiple KPIs for the comprehensive assessment of key performance indicators in rail freight systems. Additionally, the system encompasses the integration of spatio-temporal and multivariate footprint (clustering-based analytics), providing a comprehensive framework for examining the spatio-temporal dynamics of rail freight corridors. Key contribution on this work includes: i) flexibility, as it enables users to undertake a multidimensional assessment by integrating various KPI dimensions - such as efficiency, reliability, connectivity, and environmental sustainability - thereby providing a consistent basis for benchmarking across corridors; ii) weighted setting, namely normalization and weighting procedures ultimately that allow for performance measurement through composite indices on selected factors; iii) dynamic corridor analysis that accounts for the multidimensional and spatio-temporal footprint of key KPIs, derived from clustering-based methods,

complemented by statistical measures of model uncertainty (median, Q1, and Q3); iv) ranking facilities between OD corridors. With these contribution, the ADS2 provides functionality to benchmark corridors, diagnose sources of inefficiency, and dynamically compare alternative scenarios that can be aligned with diverse strategic priorities, such as maximizing capacity utilization, minimizing delays, or reducing emissions.

OD corridors in Portugal's national freight rail system, which connect one of the main strategic hubs, the Port of Sines, were used as case study for revealing corridor-specific performance footprints with the ADS2. Corridors exhibiting stable cluster profiles indicate predictable operations and consistently higher efficiency levels, suggesting that these routes are robust under normal operating conditions. In contrast, corridors characterized by heterogeneous or shifting cluster profiles reflect variable performance, highlighting potential vulnerabilities that may require further analysis or targeted interventions. For example, the Leixões - Sines corridor is represented by a cluster profile associated with a high proportion of hazardous cargo, which correlates with longer cargo handling times at the origin. The Entroncamento - Port of Sines corridor alternates between two cluster profiles. The intermittent presence of cluster "2" indicates periods where capacity utilization exceeds typical levels, resulting in longer handling times, slower travel speeds, and increased delays at the destination. These variations underscore the corridor's sensitivity to operational conditions.

Furthermore, as an exploratory and preliminary analysis, we isolated specific KPIs to examine the ranking of OD capabilities. This analysis yielded actionable insights into both environmental and terminal performance. For instance, when corridor performance was assessed in terms of cargo handling time, the Port of Sines emerged as a comparatively efficient hub relative to other terminals.

This study makes both methodological and practical contributions by enhancing the understanding of spatio-temporal corridor performance footprints while also delivering an enhanced ADS2 designed to inform freight planning and policy evaluation. Future research will include the full validating of the ADS2 with key stakeholders in the logistics sector, such as port authorities and rail operators. Furthermore, for a more comprehensive analysis of multimodal or rail freight systems, additional KPIs could be incorporated, such as freight cargo share at origin and destination terminals (multimodality), along with resilience-related indicators such as robustness (withstanding disruptions), redundancy (providing alternatives), and rapidity (speed of recovery).

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Bibliography

- [1] Ala-Laurinaho, R., Autiosalo, J., Nikander, A., Mattila, J., and Tammi, K. (2020). Data link for the creation of digital twins. *IEEE Access*, 8:228675–228684.
- [2] Andrienko, G., Andrienko, N., Fuchs, G., and Wood, J. (2016). Revealing patterns and trends of mass mobility through spatial and temporal abstraction of origin-destination movement data. *IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics*, 23(9):2120–2136.
- [3] Atluri, G., Karpatne, A., and Kumar, V. (2018). Spatio-temporal data mining: A survey of problems and methods. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 51(4):1–41.
- [4] Bahbouh, K., Wagner, J. R., Morency, C., and Berdier, C. (2017). Travel demand corridors: Modelling approach and relevance in the planning process. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 58:196–208.
- [5] Buchter, J., Grönig, J., and Nguyen, S. (2025). Ecotransit world rest-api documentation. Accessed: 2025-09-08.
- [6] Cerqueira, S., Arsenio, E., and Henriques, R. (2022). Inference of dynamic origin–destination matrices with trip and transfer status from individual smart card data. *European Transport Research Review*, 14(1):42.
- [7] Goncalves, M., Salgado, C., de Sousa, A., and Teixeira, L. (2025). Data storytelling and decision-making in seaport operations: a new approach based on business intelligence. *Sustainability*, 17(1):337.
- [8] González-Gil, A., Palacin, R., and Batty, P. (2015). Optimal energy management of urban rail systems: Key performance indicators. *Energy conversion and management*, 90:282–291.
- [9] Guo, D. (2009). Flow mapping and multivariate visualization of large spatial interaction data. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 15(6):1041–1048.
- [10] He, J., Chen, H., Chen, Y., Tang, X., and Zou, Y. (2019). Diverse visualization techniques and methods of moving-object-trajectory data: A review. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 8(2):63.
- [11] Islam, D. M. Z., Ricci, S., and Nelldal, B.-L. (2016). How to make modal shift from road to rail possible in the european transport market, as aspired to in the eu transport white paper 2011. *European transport research review*, 8(3):18.
- [12] Jing, C., Du, M., Li, S., and Liu, S. (2019). Geospatial dashboards for monitoring smart city performance. *Sustainability*, 11(20):5648.
- [13] Jong, J.-C., Suen, C.-S., and Chang, S. (2012). Decision support system to optimize railway stopping patterns: Application to taiwan high-speed rail. *Transportation Research Record*, 2289(1):24–33.
- [14] Luo, D., Cats, O., and van Lint, H. (2017). Constructing transit origin–destination matrices with spatial clustering. *Transportation Research Record*, 2652(1):39–49.
- [15] Luo, L., He, Z., Lu, Y., and Chen, J. (2020). Clarifying origin-destination flows using force-directed edge bundling layout. *IEEE Access*, 8:62572–62583.
- [16] Marchetti, D. and Wanke, P. (2020). Efficiency of the rail sections in brazilian railway system, using topsis and a genetic algorithm to analyse optimized scenarios. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 135:101858.
- [17] Marinagi, C., Reklitis, P., Trivellas, P., and Sakas, D. (2023). The impact of industry 4.0 technologies on key performance indicators for a resilient supply chain 4.0. *Sustainability*, 15(6):5185.
- [18] Papadias, D., Tao, Y., Kanis, P., and Zhang, J. (2002). Indexing spatio-temporal data warehouses. In *Proceedings 18th international conference on data engineering*, pages 166–175. IEEE.
- [19] Rahman, M. A., Alam, M. S., and Mrida, M. S. H. (2025). How interactive dashboards improve managerial decision-making in operations management. *American Journal of Advanced Technology and Engineering Solutions*, 1(01):122–146.
- [20] Rong, C., Ding, J., and Li, Y. (2024). An interdisciplinary survey on origin-destination flows modeling: Theory and techniques. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 57(1):1–49.

- [21] Serra, P. and Fancello, G. (2020). Performance assessment of alternative sss networks by combining kpis and factor-cluster analysis. *European Transport Research Review*, 12(1):57.
- [22] Shekhar, S., Jiang, Z., Ali, R. Y., Eftelioglu, E., Tang, X., Gunturi, V. M., and Zhou, X. (2015). Spatiotemporal data mining: A computational perspective. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 4(4):2306–2338.
- [23] Sobral, T., Galvão, T., and Borges, J. (2021). Knowledge-assisted visualization of multi-level origin-destination flows using ontologies. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 22(4):2168–2177.
- [24] Takman, J. and Gonzalez-Aregall, M. (2024). Public policy instruments to promote freight modal shift in europe: evidence from evaluations. *Transport Reviews*, 44(3):612–633.
- [25] Tapia, E., Lopez-Novoa, U., Sastoque-Pinilla, L., and López-de Lacalle, L. N. (2024). Implementation of a scalable platform for real-time monitoring of machine tools. *Computers in Industry*, 155:104065.
- [26] Wang, Y. and Sarkis, J. (2021). Emerging digitalisation technologies in freight transport and logistics: Current trends and future directions.
- [27] Yuan, H. and Li, G. (2021). A survey of traffic prediction: from spatio-temporal data to intelligent transportation. *Data Science and Engineering*, 6(1):63–85.
- [28] Zhou, X., Sun, J., Fu, H., Ge, F., Wu, J., and Lev, B. (2024). Resilience analysis of the integrated china-europe freight transportation network under heterogeneous demands. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 186:104130.
- [29] Zis, T. P., Psaraftis, H. N., and Reche-Vilanova, M. (2023). Design and application of a key performance indicator (kpi) framework for autonomous shipping in europe. *Maritime transport research*, 5:100095
- [30] Tang, R., De Donato, L., Besinović, N., Flammini, F., Goverde, R. M., Lin, Z., ... & Wang, Z. (2022). A literature review of Artificial Intelligence applications in railway systems. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 140, 103679.
- [31] Ali, R., Hussain, A., Nazir, S., Khan, S., & Khan, H. U. (2023). Intelligent decision support systems—An analysis of machine learning and multicriteria decision-making methods. *Applied Sciences*, 13(22), 12426.